

INJURIES AMONG CHILDREN AND SOME PECULIARITIES OF ITS SPREAD. (LITERATURE REVIEW)

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The study and analysis of current and published literature on the causes of life-threatening injuries among children, especially the medical and social aspects of injuries among school-age children.

In recent years, the rate of injuries in children in Russia is 116-118 per 1,000 children aged 0-17. The most common of these injuries is life-threatening injuries (51%). It was also found that 32.1% were committed on the street, 6.8% at school, and 4.7% in organized sports classes. The highest number of injuries was 0.9-1.1%.

In 2016, a total of 130,150 children aged 0-17 were injured in St. Petersburg, accounting for 5.3% of all cases and 55.6% of them were boys. This figure is 142.1 per 1,000 children aged 0-14. However, at the age of 15-17 years, the indicator remained

ABSTRACT

Injuries among children are still one of the most pressing and unresolved medical and social problems in medicine and health care, not only in our country, but all over the world. According to the World Health Organization, between 2000 and 2012, the number of injuries worldwide increased to 87-93 per thousand people, and more than 5 million deaths a year (10% of all deaths) are due to injuries.

In Europe, more than 120 million people are injured each year, and more than 220,000 die prematurely. If in 2013 in Russia 1,662,331 people were hospitalized with various injuries, 76.1% of them are able-bodied. 73% of all hospitalizations were due to car accidents. 43.1% of them were committed with the participation of infantry. It is noteworthy that 50% of fatalities due to car accidents occurred within minutes of the accident. Importantly, severe injuries accounted for a large number of simultaneous multiple injuries (48.4%) [1].

relatively high, at 267.7 per 1,000 children; in 2014 — 272.6; in 2015, it was -251.7. Analysis of the injuries received by their places showed that in 15-17-year-olds, injuries in life - 38%, on the street - 37%, traffic - 1.0%, at school - 11%, in organized sports classes - 7% formed. The number of children with disabilities due to injuries was 2.2 per 10,000 children across Russia. [3, 5].

Injuries among children in Russia in 2013 increased by 27 million compared to previous years and amounted to 18.8% of the total population. During the year, more

than 3 million children were admitted to having medical facilities with various injuries. Of these, 25,000 were in their first year of life, 2.5 million were children aged 1-14, and 687,000 were adolescents, 85% of whom were urban dwellers. The authors note that in rural areas, people present with more serious injuries. It is noted that 50.9% of all children's injuries are related to life-threatening injuries. In all types of injuries, the incidence in boys is 1.5 times higher. The death rate from injuries between the ages of 0 and 17 was 5.8 per 100,000 children. The incidence of injuries and bone and musculoskeletal disorders in children was 8.7 per 10,000 people. In particular, in children this figure was 2.6 ha (23.5 thousand). Among children there is a high level of negativity and mortality. Depression remains one of the leading medical and social problems, ranking second in overall morbidity among children, accounting for 6-8%. Many researchers point out that high rates of injuries among children are associated with car accidents in large cities. In children, 11.2% of primary disabilities are due to musculoskeletal disorders. 15-17% of all injured were hospitalized and treated (263 per 10,000 children). Of these, 40.3% were musculoskeletal injuries, indicating that this type of injury is more common in children (106 ± 1.3 per 10,000 children). Of the total injuries reported in children, 85-87% were musculoskeletal injuries [5, 6]. The conclusion is that the relative mobility of children leads to a high incidence of musculoskeletal injuries.

According to a study conducted in the Astrakhan region of Russia, the first place among the injuries recorded in children was injuries to the surface of the body, of which $32.2 \pm 0.27\%$ were life-

threatening. The second place was taken by injuries in life and on the street - open wounds; the third place was taken by fractures of the arm bones, including injuries in life by $15.8 \pm 0.21\%$, the fourth place was taken by the protrusion and elongation of bones by 10.0%, 0.17%. The fifth place was taken by fractures of the foot bones, of which $5.4 \pm 0.13\%$ were life-threatening injuries [7, 12, 15]. It is clear that life-threatening injuries among children occupy a significant place among the general injuries.

According to a study conducted in the Republic of Tatarstan, trauma among children and adolescents is growing. If in 2008 it was 120.3 ha per 10,000 children aged 0-17 years, in 2009 it was 122.1 ha and in 2010 it was 125.9 ha, and the main reason for this was the lack of parental responsibility and lack of supervision by the authors and the lack of awareness-raising in schools [8].

Scientific studies in Ufa have shown that the prevalence of injuries among the population, especially children, is due to a number of factors, including the prevalence of the disease among the population and the long-term nature of the disease. These include high levels of unemployment, loss of skilled labor resources and, as a result, high levels of economic losses. In almost all types of injuries, its degree is higher in men. However, in the Republic of Tatarstan in recent years the level of injuries has remained the same. (100 cases per 1,000 people) Only among adolescents there is a relative increase in injuries [9, 10]. Traumatic brain injury is the most common type of trauma and is characterized by severe complications in its course. In Russia, 600,000 people get brain injuries every year, and 50,000 people die as a

result. Half of all brain injuries in children are caused by car accidents. Of these, 44.8% were pedestrians, 41.4% were motorists, and one in 10 minor injuries was caused by a bicycle or scooter driver.

Catamnial studies showed that 12% of children with injuries did not experience any life-altering changes in their previous activities, while the parents of 88% of children with injuries showed that their children had some problems. It was also noted that 43.1% had mental disorders, 25.5% had sensory disturbances (sight, hearing, smell) and 27.5% had statodynamic (stato-dynamic) problems [11,16].

The results of scientific research conducted in Volgograd in 2012 show that the injuries inflicted on children are complex and narrow in their distribution. 36% of injuries on the surface of the body, 18% of wounds, fractures of the ankles 33.7%, protrusions 10.8%, head injuries 5.7%, burns and poisonings 3.1%, eye injuries 1, 9%, post-traumatic complications 3.8% and various injuries 1.1%. According to the author, these injuries are the most common and the leading cause of death in this life. Injuries of this type are mainly bruises, hemorrhages (hematomas), abrasions - 13.9%, wounds - 20.7%, fractures - 17.3% and burns - 6.8%. It is noted that the main part of domestic injuries occurred between 15-21 o'clock, in the spring -33% and in the fall 29.1% [13, 14, 25].

Today, a student who is brought up in a kindergarten, studying at a school desk, in the near future will be able to work in the social welfare of this country, its economic, scientific and cultural potential, as well as the national security of the state. The main injuries in children occurred in the summer months - i.e.; during the

school holidays, more precisely in May, June, July and August, accounting for 54.4% of the total injuries. [13]. Life-threatening and street injuries are among the most common in Russia. After all, if people in manufacturing and sports are injured, the whole population can be injured. Between 2004 and 2011, the rate of life-threatening injuries increased by 15.4%. [14].

According to a study conducted in Ufa, Russia, injuries are the second most common cause of disability (15%). Fractures of the limbs took the lead. Almost half of the injured (42.5%) were issued a certificate of temporary incapacity for work [15, 17].

In 2015-2017, the number of injuries among children aged 0-14 in St. Petersburg was 145.2 per 1,000 children of the same age, and 247.5 per 1,000 children aged 15-17, with no pineapple reduction and an average higher than the Russian average. Eighty-five percent of all injuries require outpatient and 15% inpatient treatment. The incidence of injuries among children with disabilities is 2.1 per 10,000 children in Russia and 0.7 hectares in St. Petersburg, which indicates the high level of specialized medical care for the injured. In Russia, trauma ranks third in the prevalence of cardiovascular disease and cancer. Each year, more than 5 million people die from injuries around the world. In Russia, more than 300,000 people die each year. Injuries caused by the external environment are 2.5 times higher in Russia than in developed countries and 1.5 times higher than in developing countries. In Russia, absent and facial injuries are among the top 10 common injuries and have a history of proliferation. [18].

Every year from August 1 to 30, Kazakhstan, together with all interested

organizations, holds a month-long campaign to prevent and reduce injuries to children and adolescents, as well as young people in life and in car accidents. Injuries among children differ from one age group to another [19]. A World Health Organization (WHO) review for Europe states that injuries among children are not only painful or disabling for children, but also have a negative impact on their physical, mental and social development, causing serious damage to society and health.

According to research conducted in a number of European countries, Greece, Ireland, Spain, Sweden and the Netherlands, the highest number of deaths from injuries among children is recorded in the districts with less wealth. The main reasons for this are the poor condition of the houses in poor areas, the lack of special playgrounds for children and the lack of adequate safety conditions, and the poor condition of the roads. According to some research, injuries are more common in children and adolescents in industrial districts than in agricultural districts. The main reasons for this are the large number and density of housing and industrial facilities, the availability of technical means and mechanisms, their lack of lifestyle and time, the large number of sports facilities in rural areas, and other reasons. 90% of injuries in children and adolescents are caused by living conditions and street conditions. [21].

In Dagestan, injuries are the third leading cause of death. Injuries have also been reported to increase with age. Injuries are more common among adolescents (47.7%) and are more common on the street, especially in the summer months. (67%) life-threatening injuries were

mostly -31% in the winter months and -28% in the fall. Injuries in boys (68%) were twice as high as in girls (32%). Among the injuries, it is noted that street and domestic injuries take the lead. [22]. The main causes of injuries among the population, especially children, are underdeveloped medical and hygienic education, non-compliance with safety rules on the street, at home, at school, at sports games, lack of technical and economic discipline in the country. Failure to do so depends in many ways on the upbringing of children in the family from an early age and other factors. According to the latest statistics in our country, the number of major injuries in children is much higher hand and foot fractures (43.0% and 34.0%, respectively). As the age of the injured increased, so did the level of hospitalization. Traditionally, injuries are higher in boys than in other countries (1.9 times). [23].

According to the World Health Organization, more than 830,000 children die each year as a result of accidents worldwide. This means that 2,300 children die every day. According to the author, these numbers are lower than the real level, because most parents do not go to the treatment and prevention facilities for minor injuries. There is also the concept of school injuries in children. A study conducted in St. Petersburg found that school injuries accounted for 17% of all child injuries. The main injuries occur during physical education classes (18%) and during breaks (42%). 76% of injuries during the break are caused by conflicts. [24].

Based on the results of the study and analysis of the literature on trauma and its complications in the population, especially

among children, the following can be concluded.

Conclusion.

Based on the results of the study and analysis of the literature on trauma and its complications among the population, especially among children, the following can be concluded.

1. Data from the World Health Organization and scientific studies conducted in a number of countries show that the prevalence of injuries among children, including domestic injuries, is high and has a tradition of proliferation, especially in developed and developing countries;

2. An analysis of the literature found that the proportion of injuries sustained in children, including injuries sustained at home, at school, on the street and at sports, was relatively high;

3. Scientific research on the medical and social aspects of trauma and its prevalence in children has been conducted mainly in the Russian Federation. In our country, including in the example of Khorezm region, the medical and social aspects of the prevalence of injuries in children are almost not studied, and this shows the need for in-depth research today.

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